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Enhanced interfacial strength of plasma treated polyethylene and glass

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Abstract

Low-temperature plasma treatment represents an important technology to influence surface properties of polymers. Less financially demanding and environmentally friendly way leads to a significant enhancement of adhesion to another type of surfaces. The article describes the influence of plasma treatment time of polyethylene (PE) powder leading to the increase of interfacial strength to glass substrate. This strength was quantified by the tensile test and compared with the industrially used chemical products, maleic anhydride or silane. The maximum value of the interfacial strength was achieved by plasma treatment with an exposure time of 60 s and is at least by 150 % higher than in the case of the interphase created by silane. The results of the research, also proven by ESCA measurement, represent the potential of using plasma treatment of powder semi-products for the preparation of fibre-reinforced composites with a thermoplastic matrix processed only at atmospheric pressures.

Keywords: Plastics; Glass; Surface treatment; Interface/interphase

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